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Potentiometric Studies on Ternary Complexes of Nickel (II)

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THE survey of the literature reveals that the stereochemistry¹ of Ni(II)-thiosalicylic acid complex $H[NiL_3].2C_2H_5OH$ (L=thiosalicylic acid) has been discussed. Whereas salicylic acid has very little or no tendency to form chelate with nickel², thiosalicylic acid (TSA) forms 1 : 1 Ni (II)-TSA chelate in the pH range 3-6. In the present communication the results on the potentiometric studies of the ternary systems: Ni(II)-TSA-gly/tiron/en/pn (where gly=glycine, tiron=1,2-dihydroxy-benzene-3, 5-disulfonic acid disodium salt, en=ethylenediamine, pn=1,2-propylenediamine) have been discussed and formation constants ($\log K_{MAB}$), free energies of formation (ΔF°) for the resulting complexes have been calculated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Analar BDH or E. Merck grade and en and pn were used as their dihydrochlorides. .025 M TSA solution was prepared in absolute ethanol. The concentrations of ligand solutions were checked by potentiometric titrations and Ni estimated gravimetrically by the usual method. All the titrations were carried out in duplicate at temperature $25^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ keeping the total volume of solution (50 ml in 20% ethanol) and ionic strength (0.1 M KNO_3) constant. pH measurements were made with a Philips Precision pH meter (PR 9405 M).

Calculations

pK values of the ligands were calculated by the method of Chebarek and Martell³ (Table 1), formation constants ($\log K_{MAB}$) by the method of Thompson and Loraas⁴ and free energies of formation (ΔF°) by the expression : $\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K_{MAB}$ (Table 2).

TABLE 1

Ligands	pK ₁	pK ₂
en	7.05	9.75
pn	6.91	9.78
gly	—	9.79
tiron	7.67	12.48 ^{Ref 5}

TABLE 2

Ternary system	$\log K_{MAB}$	ΔF° (kcal/degree/mole)
Ni(II)-TSA-gly	$5.125 \pm .015$	- 6.97
Ni(II)-TSA-tiron	$7.88 \pm .15$	- 10.71
Ni(II)-TSA-en	$6.09 \pm .05$	- 8.28
Ni(II)-TSA-pn	$3.40 \pm .18$	- 4.62

Results and Discussion

In the curve x representing the titration of 1:1 Ni (II)-TSA, a sharp inflexion at m=2 may be attributed to the formation of a light purple 1:1 chelate which probably disproportionates at a higher pH into 1:2 Ni (II)-TSA complex and metal hydroxide giving a second inflexion at m = 3.

Curves a, b, c, and d represent 1:1:1 Ni(II)-TSA-gly/tiron/en/pn ternary systems respectively. In all these cases 1:1 Ni (II)-TSA chelate is initially formed which is evidenced by (i) a light purple colour of the solution (ii) almost superimposable nature of the curves for the ternary systems with the curve x for the binary Ni(II)-TSA system upto $m \approx 2$. Addition of the secondary ligand, however, takes place afterwards giving an inflexion at $m \approx 4$ (at $m = 3$ in the case of gly).

The formation of mixed ligand complexes in all the systems is further supported by :

- (i) non-appearance of a solid phase and a different colour observed during the titration ;
- (ii) the lowering in pH in comparison to binary systems ; and
- (iii) non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves a', b', c', and d' (drawn by adding horizontal distances of Ni(II)-TSA and free secondary ligand curves) with the corresponding curves a, b, c and d for the mixed ligand systems in the region of ternary complex formation.

From the foregoing discussion it is, therefore, evident that in all these cases ternary complexes are formed and the order of stability in terms of secondary ligand is found to be as tiron > en > gly > pn.

Fig. 1.

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Interaction of 4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Anhydride with Phthalic Anhydride : Synthesis of 6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-Carboxy)-Phenylisocoumarins and Related Substances :

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APPPLICATION of the phthaloylation reaction¹ with phthalic anhydride in pyridine to 4, 5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) gave directly 4-carboxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (II) in good yield, the reaction having taken place in the same manner as already explained in case of homophthalic and 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydrides¹.

The investigations on the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (II) as depicted in the chart have led to easy synthesis of the isocoumarin (III), the 3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII) and the other related substances that are of importance particularly because of the methoxy groups in position 6 and 7, commonly found in natural products.

Experimental

4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) : It was prepared by refluxing 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid² (5 g.) with acetic anhydride (10 ml) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The crystals separated on cooling were washed with ether and sublimed under reduced pressure to obtain the anhydride (4 g), m.p. 175°-76°. (Found : C, 59.7 ; H, 4.4 ; C₁₁H₁₀O₅ requires C, 59.9 and H, 4.5%).

4-Carboxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (II) : 4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I, 1 g), phthalic anhydride (1.5 g) and dry pyridine (6 ml) were mixed and stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and left at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice containing dil. HCl and was allowed to stand for 2 hrs. The separated solid crystallised from acetic acid as shining cubes, m. p. 258° (decomp), yield 1.4 g. (Found : C, 61.3 ; H, 4.2. C₁₉H₁₄O₈ requires C, 61.6 and H, 3.8%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 245 nm (log ϵ : 4.59).

When however the same reaction was carried out at the temperature of boiling water bath for 3 hr and the product (1.3 g, m. p. 210-25°) was boiled with methanol (25 ml) only a part went into solution. The insoluble part yielded II (0.55 g) while the methanolic solution on concentration (charcoal) and cooling afforded the isocoumarin III (0.55 g) described below.

